

Metal Complexes of *p, p'*-bis(thiocarbamoyl) benzene[†]

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A few metal chelates of the type, M(BTCB), where [M=Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Pd(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Mg(II), Ba(II) and Pb(II)]; and BTCB=*p, p'*-bis(thiocarbamoyl) benzene] have been prepared and characterised. All these chelates are highly insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. The bonding of the ligand to metal ion through sulphur and amine nitrogen has been proposed from i. r. spectrum. Normal magnetic moment is observed in case of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Mn(II) chelates except Pd(II) complex which is diamagnetic. These chelates show octahedral arrangement of the ligand around the central metal ion.

THE *p, p'*-bis(thiocarbamoyl) benzene is a thiourea derivative of *p*-phenylene diamine reported earlier¹. As a part of our study on the synthesis of metal chelates with different thiourea derivatives we report here a few metal chelates of *p, p'*-bis(thiocarbamoyl) benzene with bivalent metal ions.

Methods and Materials :

The ligand H₂NCSNHC₆H₄NHCSNH₂, (H₂-BTCB) was prepared following the procedure reported by Nayak and coworkers¹.

Preparation of the Chelates :

A weighed quantity of the ligand (2.26 g) was suspended in water and dissolved by adding a minimum volume of 0.1 N sodium hydroxide. This was then added to an equimolar aqueous solution of appropriate salt, when the chelate got readily precipitated. The precipitate was digested on a water bath for about thirty minutes, then filtered, washed

with water followed by alcohol and dried in vacuum and analysed.

The metal content of each complex was determined according to standard procedures. Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate². The nitrogen content was determined by semi-micro combustion process. The analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

The complexes are found to be insoluble in water and most of common organic solvents.

Physical measurements :

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the solid complexes at room temperatures were made by Gouy methods, using mercury (II)-tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) as the calibrating agent. The diamagnetic corrections were made using the values given by Lewis and Wilkins³. Infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in KBr

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE LIGAND AND ITS METAL CHELATES

Formula of the Compounds.	Colour	μ_{eff} in B.M.	Metal%		Sulphur%		Nitrogen%	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. H ₂ BTCB	Yellowish-white				28.24	28.81	24.62	24.77
2. [Cu(BTCB)]	Grey	2.01	22.30	21.95	21.93	22.14	19.01	19.32
3. [Ni(BTCB)]	Dirty-green	3.70	20.81	20.70	22.28	22.49	19.19	19.64
4. [Co(BTCB)]	Light-green	4.26	21.00	20.68	22.43	22.49	19.22	19.64
5. [Mn(BTCB)]	Brown	5.85	20.01	19.59	22.97	22.77	19.96	19.92
6. [Pd(BTCB)]	Violet	Diamagnetic	32.20	32.00	18.95	19.27	16.23	16.85
7. [Zn(BTCB)]	White		22.21	22.40	21.82	21.99	18.87	19.20
8. [Cd(BTCB)]	Yellow		33.12	33.21	18.68	18.9	15.92	16.50
9. [Hg(BTCB)]	White		47.86	47.49	14.92	15.00	12.81	13.13
10. [Pb(BTCB)]	Grey		47.82	47.80	13.32	14.80	12.76	12.93
11. [Mg(BTCB)]	White		9.21	9.60	25.32	25.60	21.94	22.38
12. [Ba(BTCB)]	White		37.34	37.70	17.83	17.30	15.06	15.41

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TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS OF THE LIGAND AND ITS METAL CHELATES IN cm^{-1} .

Ligand H_2BTCB	[Cu'(BTCB)]	[Ni(BTCB)]	[Co(BTCB)]	[Mn(BTCB)]	[Zn'(BTCB)]	[Cd(BTCB)]	Assignment
3300-3100s, bd	3300s	3300s	3300m	3340s	3300s	3300-3120s, bd	$\nu(\text{N-H})$
	3220s	3240w	3240s	3240m	3240w		
	3120w	3140w	3140w	3150w	3140m		
2990w	3000s	2990w	2980w	3000w	3300s	2960m	$\nu(\text{C-H})$
2900w		2900w	2900m	2910w	2990w		
2820w	2890w		2860w				$\nu(\text{S-H})$
2640w	—	—	—	—	—	—	$\nu(\text{C=N})$
	2070s	2050m, bd	2100w, bd	—	2140w, bd	2100s	$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$
1610s	1600s	1610s	1605w	1600m	1605s	1600s	
1540s	1535s	1530s	1535s	1540s	1530s	1500m	
1500m		1500m	1500s	1510m	1520m	1525m	
1470s	1490s	1470s	1475s	1475s	1485w	—	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NCN})$
1410s	1405w	1410s	1400s	1420s	1405s	1410m	$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{NCN}) +$
1305s	1300w, bd	1310s	1305s	1310s	1320s	1315s	$\nu(\text{C=S})$
1220s	1235m	1225s	1230s	1225s	1230s	1220w	$\delta(\text{NH}_2) + \nu(\text{C-N})$
1110w	1100vw	1120vw	—	1120vw	1120vw	1155s	
1070s	1000m	1020w	1020s	1025w	1060w	1085m	$\delta(\text{NH}_2) + \nu(\text{C=N})$
—	—	—	950vw	—	950w	—	
880m	865vw	880w	885w	—	885vw	875s	
845s	845s	—	860s	—	840s, bd	855w	
825m	825s, bd	825m	835vw	—	—	—	
785s	765w	770s	780s	760s	745s, bd	750w	$\nu(\text{C-S}) + \nu(\text{C-N})$
	705w	—	—	—	—	—	
680s, bd	—	685s, bd	690w, bd	680vw	—	—	
650s	660vw	655w	655vw	—	665w	680vw	
615w, bd	615vw	620vw	620w	630vw	—	—	

N.B. s=strong, w=weak, m=medium, vw=very weak, bd=broad.

phase on a Perkin-Elmer model 221 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the complexes were taken in nujol mull and that of the ligand in acetone.

Results and Discussion

The ligand *p, p'*-bis(thiocarbamoyl) benzene can be structurally represented in a variety of ways.

The important vibrational bands of the ligand and a few metal chelates are recorded in Table 2. In the higher frequency region $3300\text{-}3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ the ligand shows a strong and broad band which is attributed to the $\nu(\text{NH})$ vibration. The metal complexes of the ligand show a splitting in this region indicating the involvement of NH group in bond formation⁴. As reported⁵ the $\nu(\text{NH})$ bands are sharper in the metal complexes than the thiourea itself and the hydrogen bonding present in the free ligand, disappears in the metal complexes. The strong ligand band near about 3000 cm^{-1} which remains

almost unaffected in the metal chelates is attributed to the $\nu(\text{CH})$ vibration of benzene ring.

A weak band is observed in the ligand at about 2640 cm^{-1} and has been assigned to (S-H) stretching vibration of the thiol form II(b). This assignment is further strengthened as it does not occur in the metal complexes where the S-H bond has been broken down in the formation of inner metal complexes⁶.

In the frequency region $1650\text{-}1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the spectra of the ligand is quite complex, but in sharp contrast, the metal complexes show a relatively few well defined bands. The first strong band in the ligand appears at 1610 cm^{-1} followed by another band of nearly equal intensity at about 1540 cm^{-1} . These two bands shift to a lower frequency region in the metal complexes and appear near about 1600 cm^{-1} and 1500 cm^{-1} respectively. We assign the high frequency band to C=N stretching vibrations of the form II(b) and the low frequency one to NH_2 deformation vibrations. The shift of the high frequency band to lower frequency can be due to coordination of the nitrogen atom of the C=N group to the metal ion while that of the low frequency band to further lower frequency may be due to the breakdown of the hydrogen bond involving NH_2 groups as observed in the solid ligand.

The strong band appearing at about 1470 cm^{-1} in the free thiocarbamide assigned mainly to NCN

asymmetric stretching⁷ is shifted to the higher frequency region in all the metal complexes corresponding to an increased double bond character of the C-N bond because of sulphur coordination to the metal. Similarly the low frequency band at $\sim 1410\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand assigned mostly to $\nu(\text{NCN})_{\text{sym}}$ and $\nu(\text{CS})$ shifts to a lower frequency region in the metal complexes and overlaps with the neighbouring bands of the ligand around 1300 cm^{-1} .

In the spectra of the ligand there appear two strong bands at about 1220 cm^{-1} while in the spectra of the metal chelates the former remains almost unaffected and the latter disappears giving rise to only one strong band at 1020 cm^{-1} . These bands most probably arise due to deformation or rocking mode of vibration for the NH_2 groups or a combination of NH_2 rocking and C-N stretching vibration.

A sharp and strong band at about 785 cm^{-1} in the ligand attributed to combination bands of $\nu(\text{C-S})$ and $\nu(\text{C-N})$, on coordination with metal complexes shifts to a lower frequency region and appears near about 750 cm^{-1} clearly implying the coordination of sulphur and nitrogen atoms of the structural form II(b) in the metal complexes.

Electronic Spectra and Magnetic Properties :

The Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Mn(II) complexes are paramagnetic whereas the Pd(II) complex is diamagnetic. A broad asymmetry band of Cu(II) complex located at $18,570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ approximates to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in an octahedral ligand field. Tetragonal distortion and Jahn-Teller effect can be suggested because of its width and asymmetry character. Besides, a charge transfer band appears $\sim 23,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Important transitions of Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes are observed near about $16,500$ and $24,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $15,450$ and $17,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The ligand field band of the former can be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ while the latter to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\text{P})$ transition in a nearly octahedral field.

The chelates probably possess polymeric structure wherein each ligand molecule (Fig. IIb) coordinates towards two metal ions in trans bi-bidentate form involving sulphur and nitrogen atoms (Fig. III). High insolubility in water and common organic solvents of the chelates support the polymeric structure. The octahedral field may be due to intermolecular out of plane coordination through sulphur atom.

III.

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